

A CORRELATION STUDY BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG PRIMARY TEACHER

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***Abstract:** The present research deals with Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher. The samples comprise 60 rural and urban Primary Teacher by using Purposive sampling technique. The tools used for present research are Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire prepared by investigator. The data was analyzed using r .*

Findings

There is significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Emotionally intelligent

Introduction:

The term job satisfaction figures prominently in any discussions on management of human resources. Job satisfaction refers to a person's feeling of satisfaction on the job, which acts as a motivation to work. It is not the self satisfaction, happiness or self- contentment but the satisfaction on the job

Job satisfaction is a set of favorable or unfavorable feelings and emotions with which employees view their work. Job satisfaction is an affective attitude a feeling of relative like or dislike toward something (for example, a satisfied employee may comment that "I enjoy variety of tasks to do"). There is an important difference between these job-related feelings of satisfaction and two other elements of employee attitudes. The same employee may have an intellectual response to her

work, stating the objective thought (belief) that "my work is quit complex". On another occasion, the employee may voice her behavioral intensions to a coworker ("I plan to quit this job in three months"). Attitudes, then, consist of feelings, thoughts, and intentions to act

Emotions are involved in everything people do: every action, decision and judgment. Emotionally intelligent people recognize this and use their thinking to manage their emotions rather than being managed by them. In the course of last two decades, Emotional Intelligence (EI) concept has become a very important indicator of a person's knowledge, skills and abilities in workplace, school and personal life. The overall result of researches suggests that EI plays a significant role in the job performance, motivation, decision making, successful management and leadership. Thus applying EI methodology in higher education can have lots of benefits for students. It not only fulfills their desire but also makes them more efficient in their field.

Hence the investigators selected the topic Correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher.

Statement of the Problem

"A Correlation study between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence Job Satisfaction among Primary Teacher."

Objective

1. To identify the correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher.
2. To identify the correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of male Primary Teacher.
3. To identify the correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of female Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher.
2. There is no significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of male Primary Teacher.
3. There is no significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of female Primary Teacher.

Methodology of the study: Descriptive survey method has been used for the study of the Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher .The sample comprise for the present study is 60 Primary Teacher. Purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data. The following tools were used to collect the data from Primary Teacher. Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire prepared by investigator. The obtained data was analyzed by using the Statistical techniques viz. correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation: The collected data is subjected to statistical analysis and the results obtained are as given below.

Hypotheses:

1. **There is no significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher.**

	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
Primary Teacher	Job Satisfaction	60	58	.76	.250
	Emotional Intelligence				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is .250 and the obtain 'r' value is .76 So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

- 2 There is no significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of male Primary Teacher.

	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
Male Primary Teacher.	Job Satisfaction	30	28	0.68	.361
	Emotional Intelligence				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.361 and the obtain 'r' value is 0.68. So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of male Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

- 3 There is no significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Female Primary Teacher.

	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
Female Primary Teacher.	Job Satisfaction	30	28	0.69	.361
	Emotional Intelligence				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.361 and the obtained 'r' value is 0.69. So the obtained 'r' value is greater than the table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of the obtained 'r' value; we can say that, there is a significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of female Primary Teacher.

Findings

1. There is a significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher.
2. There is a significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of male Primary Teacher.
3. There is a significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of female Primary Teacher.

Conclusion

The findings of the present study show that a significant correlation between Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence of Primary Teacher is observed in the case of male, female Primary Teacher.

Reference

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